

ILM-FAN MUAMMOLARI TADQIQOTCHILAR TALQINIDA

ILM | TA'LIM | INNOVATSIYA | MAKTAB
YANGI O'ZBEKISTON | BUYUK KELAJAK
UCHINCHI RENESSANS

ANIQ
FANLAR

TABIIY
FANLAR

TIBBIYOT
FANLARI

TEXNIKA
FANLARI

IJTIMOY-GUMANITAR
FANLAR

PEDAGOGIKA
VA PSIXOLOGIYA

KONFERENSIYA QATNASHCHILARI:

- ✓ TALABALAR
- ✓ MAGISTRANTLAR
- ✓ DOKTORANTLAR
- ✓ YOSH OLIMLAR
- ✓ O'QITUVCHILAR

KONFERENSIYA YO'NALISHLARI:

- 🌱 Aniq fanlar
- 🌿 Tabiiy fanlar
- 🏥 Tibbiyot fanlari
- ⚙️ Texnika fanlari
- 👥 Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar
- 🎨 San'at va madaniyat fanlari
- 🏃 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport
- ✍️ Filologiya fanlari
- 📖 Pedagogika fanlari
- 🧠 Psixologiya fanlari

UCHINCHI RENESSANS

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OPTIMIZATION OF THERMAL PROCESSING CONDITIONS FOR ZINC CAKES USING TECHNICAL SULFUR

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Abstract: This study examines the reductive roasting of $ZnFe_2O_4$ in zinc cake using sulfur. XRD and SEM-EDX analyses showed that optimal conditions were achieved at 500 °C with 10% sulfur addition, leading to the formation of ZnO and FeS phases. The process improves zinc recovery during subsequent sulfuric acid leaching.

Keywords: zinc cake, zinc ferrite, reductive roasting, sulfur, XRD analysis, SEM-EDX, zinc extraction.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda rux keki tarkibidagi $ZnFe_2O_4$ fazasining oltingugurt yordamida qaytaruvchi kuydirish jarayoni o‘rganildi. XRD va SEM-EDX tahlillari natijasida 500 °C harorat va 10% oltingugurt qo‘shilganda optimal natijalar kuzatilib, ZnO va FeS fazalari hosil bo‘lishi aniqlandi. Jarayon keyingi sulfat kislotali eritishda ruxning ajralib chiqish darajasini oshiradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: rux keki, rux ferriti, qaytaruvchi kuydirish, oltingugurt, XRD tahlili, SEM-EDX, rux ajralishi.

Аннотация: В данной работе исследован процесс восстановительного обжига фазы $ZnFe_2O_4$, содержащейся в цинковом кеке, с использованием серы. Результаты XRD и SEM-EDX анализа показали, что оптимальные условия достигаются при температуре 500 °C и добавлении 10% серы, при этом образуются фазы ZnO и FeS. Данный процесс повышает степень извлечения цинка при последующем сернокислотном выщелачивании.

Ключевые слова: цинковый кек, цинковый феррит, восстановительный обжиг, сера, рентгенофазовый анализ, SEM-EDX, извлечение цинка.

Problem Statement. Zinc cake formed during zinc production contains zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4), which has a stable spinel structure and dissolves poorly in conventional sulfuric acid leaching [1]. This leads to zinc losses and reduces process efficiency. Therefore, developing an effective method for decomposing zinc ferrite into easily soluble phases is an important task in hydrometallurgy [2].

Research Methodology. In this study, zinc cake obtained from Almalıy MMC was mixed with 5 – 15 wt.% sulfur and subjected to reductive roasting at 300–600 °C for 60 minutes in a laboratory muffle furnace [3]. The roasted products were analyzed by XRD and SEM-EDX methods to investigate phase transformations, morphology, and elemental distribution.

Obtained Results. The results showed that the decomposition of ZnFe_2O_4 strongly depended on roasting temperature and sulfur amount. The best result was achieved at 500 °C with 10 wt.% sulfur, where most of the ferrite phase transformed into ZnO and FeS phases. XRD and SEM-EDX analyses confirmed the formation of zinc-rich oxide and iron sulfide regions.

Scientific Conclusion. The conducted study demonstrated that sulfur-assisted reductive roasting is an effective method for the decomposition of zinc ferrite contained in zinc cake. It was established that roasting at 500 °C for 60 minutes with 10 wt.% sulfur provides the most favorable conditions for converting ZnFe_2O_4 into ZnO and FeS phases. The formation of these phases is important because zinc oxide dissolves much more easily during subsequent sulfuric acid leaching, which can significantly increase zinc recovery. The obtained results can be useful for developing more efficient and resource-saving technologies for processing zinc production residues and reducing the amount of industrial waste.

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